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**DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF LANDSCAPE EDUCATION:
INTEGRATION OF BIM, GIS AND VR/AR TECHNOLOGIES IN THE
TRAINING OF NEW GENERATION SPECIALISTS**
**ЦИФРОВАЯ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ ЛАНДШАФТНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ:
ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ BIM, GIS И VR/AR В ПОДГОТОВКЕ
СПЕЦИАЛИСТОВ НОВОГО ПОКОЛЕНИЯ**

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***Аннотация:** В статье рассматриваются современные тенденции цифровой трансформации ландшафтного образования в условиях активного внедрения технологий информационного моделирования, пространственного анализа и иммерсивной визуализации. Актуальность исследования обусловлена необходимостью подготовки специалистов нового поколения, способных эффективно осуществлять профессиональную деятельность в цифровой среде и использовать современные инструменты проектирования территорий и ландшафтных объектов. Цель исследования заключается в теоретическом обосновании и разработке концептуальной модели интеграции BIM, GIS и VR/AR технологий в систему подготовки специалистов ландшафтного профиля. Методологическую основу исследования составили системный, компетентностный, интегративный и средовой подходы. В работе использованы методы анализа научной литературы, сравнительного анализа отечественного и зарубежного опыта, структурно-функционального моделирования и обобщения современных образовательных практик.*

***Abstract.** The article examines current trends in the digital transformation of landscape education in the context of the active introduction of information modeling, spatial analysis and immersive visualization technologies. The relevance of the research is determined by the need to train a new generation of specialists who are able to effectively carry out professional activities in a digital environment and use modern tools for designing territories and landscape facilities. The purpose of the research is to theoretically substantiate and develop a conceptual model for integrating BIM, GIS and VR/AR technologies into the training system for landscape specialists. The*

methodological basis of the study was based on systemic, competence-based, integrative and environmental approaches. The paper uses methods of scientific literature analysis, comparative analysis of domestic and foreign experience, structural and functional modeling and generalization of modern educational practices.

Ключевые слова: *цифровая трансформация, BIM-технологии, GIS-технологии, виртуальная реальность, цифровая образовательная среда, профессиональная подготовка, цифровые компетенции.*

Keywords: *digital transformation, BIM technologies, GIS technologies, virtual reality, digital educational environment, professional training, digital competencies.*

Introduction. The modern education system in the field of landscape architecture is in the stage of deep transformation due to the active development of digital technologies for the design and management of territorial systems. The transition to the digital environment creates new requirements for the professional competencies of specialists, including the ability to work with integrated information models, spatial data and visualization tools.

Traditional teaching methods based on graphic drawing, prototyping and static visualization are largely losing their effectiveness in the context of digitalization of professional activity. Information modeling technologies (BIM), geographic information systems (GIS), as well as virtual and augmented reality (VR/AR) tools are widely used in modern design practice, providing comprehensive analysis, modeling and presentation of design solutions.

At the same time, an analysis of existing educational programs shows that the introduction of these technologies is fragmented and does not provide a holistic formation of professional competencies. This leads to a gap between the

requirements of the professional environment and the level of graduate training.

In this regard, there is a need to rethink the content and structure of the educational process in the field of landscape architecture, aimed at integrating digital technologies and developing interdisciplinary skills appropriate to modern conditions of project activity.

The purpose of the study is to identify effective approaches and develop a model for the implementation of BIM, GIS and VR/AR technologies in the educational process for the formation of professional competencies of a new generation of specialists in the field of landscape design.

Research objectives:

- to analyze current trends in the digitalization of education in the context of training specialists in the field of landscape architecture;
- explore the functionality of BIM, GIS, and VR/AR technologies in landscape design practice;
- identify the pedagogical potential and educational advantages of using digital technologies;

– to develop an integration model of the educational process based on the use of digital tools;

– to identify the main problems and limitations of the introduction of digital technologies in the educational process.

The digital transformation of education involves the transition from a linear learning model to an integrated digital environment in which design, analysis and visualization take place in a single information space.

BIM is considered as the basis of information modeling of objects. BIM technologies allow you to create information models of landscape objects that combine architectural, engineering and environmental parameters. In the educational process, BIM promotes the development of systems thinking and integrated design skills.

GIS technologies provide analysis of territories, assessment of natural conditions and planning constraints. Their use in teaching allows students to work with real spatial data, increasing the accuracy of design decisions.

VR/AR technologies of virtual and augmented reality create conditions for immersive learning. Students can visualize design solutions in a real environment, which increases the level of perception of space and the quality of design solutions.

VR/AR technologies allow you to:

- visualize the project in real time;
- simulate human - environment interaction;
- to increase the level of spatial perception among students.

This model ensures the continuity of the educational process from the analysis of the territory to the implementation of the project.

Materials and methods of research. The research materials are theoretical and practical sources reflecting current trends in the digitalization of landscape education and the introduction of digital technologies in architectural and spatial design.

The study included:

- Scientific publications on BIM, GIS, and VR/AR technologies in education and design;
- International and national standards for digital modeling and geo-information systems;
- educational programs for training specialists in the field of landscape architecture and related fields;
- Analytical reports and methodological recommendations on the digital transformation of higher education;
- cases of implementation of digital platforms in architectural and landscape practice.

The object of the research is a system of professional training of specialists in the field of landscape architecture.

The subject of the research is the processes of digital transformation of the educational environment based on the integration of BIM, GIS and VR/AR technologies.

The research methodology is based on a combination of the following scientific approaches:

- A systematic approach that allows us to consider the educational process as an integrated digital ecosystem;
- A competence-based approach focused on the formation of professional, digital and interdisciplinary competencies;
- An activity-based approach that provides an analysis of educational activities through project and practice-oriented tasks;
- An integrative approach involving the integration of BIM, GIS and VR/AR into a single educational environment;
- An environmental approach that considers a digital educational platform as a developing professional learning environment.

The work used a combination of theoretical and empirical-analytical methods.:

Theoretical methods:

- analysis of scientific literature and normative sources;
- comparative analysis of foreign and domestic experience;
- modeling of the digital educational environment;

Systematization and classification of digital technologies in education.

Empirical and analytical methods:

- content analysis of educational programs;
- expert assessment of the integration possibilities of BIM, GIS and VR/AR;
- analysis of pedagogical cases of digital technology implementation;

- Generalization of the practice of project-based learning in landscape architecture.

Modeling methods:

- structural and functional modeling of the digital educational ecosystem;
- designing an integration model of BIM–GIS–VR/AR interaction;
- Visualization of educational scenarios in a digital environment.

The research was conducted in stages:

1. The analytical stage is the study of theoretical sources and the identification of key areas of digital transformation of landscape education.

2. The system modeling stage is the development of a conceptual model for the integration of BIM, GIS and VR/AR technologies.

3. The synthetic stage is the generalization of the results and the formation of methodological recommendations for the introduction of digital tools into the educational process.

The scientific novelty of the research lies in the development of the theoretical and methodological foundations of the digital transformation of landscape education by substantiating and structuring the integration of BIM, GIS and VR/AR technologies as a single educational system.

The following new scientific results were obtained in the framework of the conducted research:

1. A conceptual model of BIM–GIS–VR/AR integration in landscape education has been formed. In contrast to existing approaches that consider these

technologies in isolation, their systemic interrelation is proposed, where GIS acts as a source of spatial data, BIM is a tool for parametric modeling, and VR/AR is an environment for immersive visualization and educational interaction.

2. The integration approach to the digital educational environment of landscape architecture is substantiated. It is shown that the effectiveness of training new generation specialists is achieved not through the introduction of individual digital tools, but through their integrated integration into a single educational ecosystem.

3. The structure of digital competencies of future landscape specialists has been clarified. The key competence groups are identified: spatial-analytical (GIS), design-information (BIM), visual-immersive (VR/AR), as well as integrative digital competencies that ensure intertechnological interaction.

4. An approach has been developed to transform the traditional learning model into a project-based digital environment. It is shown that the transition to a digital learning model changes the nature of the educational process: from the reproductive acquisition of knowledge to modeling real professional situations in a digital environment.

5. The pedagogical conditions for the effective implementation of digital transformation have been identified. These include: the availability of an integrated digital platform, the training of teaching staff, the use of project-oriented teaching methods and the provision of interdisciplinary interaction.

Analysis of domestic and foreign research. In the context of the digital transformation of society, the issues of modernization of vocational education are becoming one of the priority areas of scientific research. This problem is becoming particularly relevant in the field of landscape architecture, where design activities are increasingly based on the use of digital modeling technologies, spatial analysis and visualization. An analysis of domestic and foreign studies shows that in recent years there has been a steady increase in interest in integrating BIM, GIS and VR/AR technologies into the educational process. In foreign scientific literature, the digital transformation of education is considered as the process of forming new learning models based on the use of digital platforms, information modeling technologies and intelligent project support systems. A significant contribution to the development of the digital design concept was made by the work of Charles Eastman and his colleagues, in which BIM is considered as a tool for integrated lifecycle management of design facilities. The researchers emphasize that the use of BIM technologies in the educational process contributes to the development of systems thinking, interdisciplinary interaction skills and digital design.

Landscape architecture research focuses on the integration of BIM and GIS. Foreign authors note that the combination of information modeling and geoinformation systems makes it possible to take into account the spatial, ecological and infrastructural characteristics of the

territory even at the design stage. This approach helps students develop the skills of complex analysis of landscape systems and making informed design decisions.

A separate area of research is related to the use of virtual and augmented reality technologies. According to foreign scientists, VR/AR technologies provide a qualitatively new level of interaction between students and the designed space, allowing them to simulate real-world scenarios for the operation of facilities, analyze compositional solutions and conduct virtual experiments. As a result, the level of spatial perception and the quality of project training of future specialists increases. In recent years, the concept of an Immersive Learning Environment has been actively developing in foreign universities, involving the integration of BIM, GIS and VR/AR into a single digital platform. Such solutions are used in educational programs on. In the Russian scientific literature, the issues of digital transformation of education are considered mainly in the context of the modernization of the educational environment, the introduction of digital platforms and the development of digital competencies of students. The researchers note that the digitalization of higher education contributes to the transition from the traditional model of knowledge transfer to the model of active project-based learning. At the same time, the use of information modeling technologies, electronic educational resources and interactive visualization tools are becoming key areas of development. In the field of architectural and landscape

education, domestic research is mainly devoted to the implementation of BIM technologies in the design training of students, the use of geoinformation systems for the analysis of territories and the use of three-dimensional modeling tools in the educational process. At the same time, the analysis of publications shows that most of the works consider these technologies separately from each other, without forming a single digital educational environment.

Educational organizations in Kazakhstan are characterized by a tendency to gradually introduce digital technologies into the training of architects, designers and landscape specialists. However, existing research indicates the need to develop new methodological approaches that ensure the integrated integration of digital tools into the educational process. A comparison of domestic and foreign studies allows us to identify a number of significant features.

First, foreign research is focused on creating integrated digital learning ecosystems in which BIM, GIS, and VR/AR function as interconnected elements of a unified educational environment. In domestic practice, an approach based on the introduction of individual digital tools into existing educational programs prevails.

Secondly, foreign authors focus on the development of interdisciplinary competencies and digital design thinking, while domestic research is more often focused on the technical development of software tools.

Thirdly, the analysis shows that the issues of integrating BIM, GIS and VR/AR are insufficiently developed in the landscape education system, which indicates that there is a scientific niche for further research.

The analysis of domestic and foreign studies allows us to draw the following conclusions:

- the digital transformation of landscape education is a stable global trend;
- BIM, GIS and VR/AR are considered as key technologies for training new generation specialists;
- The most effective educational models are based on the integration of these technologies into a single digital environment;
- In domestic practice, the issues of integrated use of BIM, GIS and VR/AR in landscape education have not been sufficiently developed;
- There is an objective need to create a conceptual model of a digital educational ecosystem that ensures the formation of professional and digital competencies of future specialists in the field of landscape architecture.

The identified provisions served as the basis for the development of the

author's model for the integration of BIM, GIS and VR/AR technologies in the training system for landscape specialists.

The results of the study revealed the following limitations of traditional education:

1. the gap between theory and practice;
2. lack of integration of digital tools;
3. Weak interdisciplinarity of training;
4. limited visualization of design solutions.

The advantages of the digital integration of BIM, GIS and VR/AR ensure the continuity of the project process, improve the quality of design solutions, develop digital competencies and adapt to the requirements of the modern labor market. The BIM–GIS–VR/AR integration model in education includes three levels:

Level 1 is GIS analysis. Spatial data collection, territory analysis, and constraint assessment.

Level 2 — BIM modeling. Creation of an information model of an object, development of design solutions and integration of engineering data.

Level 3 — VR/AR visualization. Immersive project presentation, spatial perception assessment, and correction of design decisions. The model reflects a consistent transition from territory analysis to design and visualization. It ensures the logical coherence of the educational process, the integration of theory and practice, and the formation of digital thinking.

TECHNOLOGY INTEGRATION SCHEME

Figure 1 — BIM–GIS–VR/AR integration model in landscape education.

The proposed model can be used in university landscape architecture programs, in the development of educational standards, in design bureaus for student internships and in the creation of digital laboratories. The integration of BIM, GIS and VR/AR technologies forms a new educational environment focused on practice-oriented learning. Pedagogical effects. The implementation of the model helps to increase students' motivation, develop spatial thinking, develop project competencies and improve the quality of graduation papers. The main problems are in limiting implementation. The high cost of software, insufficient teacher training, technical limitations of educational institutions, and the need to update curricula. Development prospects. Further development is associated with the introduction of artificial intelligence into design, the development of digital territory doubles and the expansion of interdisciplinary training programs. Nevertheless, global experience shows that the transition to digital educational models is an inevitable stage in the development of landscape architecture.

Conclusion. Digital transformation is one of the key factors in the modernization of modern higher education and has a significant impact on the content, methods and organization of professional training of specialists in the field of landscape architecture. With the active introduction of digital technologies, there is an increasing need for future specialists to develop not only professional knowledge

and skills, but also digital competencies that ensure effective work with information models, spatial data, and immersive visualization tools. The analysis of domestic and foreign studies has shown that BIM, GIS and VR/AR technologies are becoming the most important tools for digital design and spatial environment management. At the same time, it has been established that in the existing educational practice, these technologies are often used separately, which reduces the effectiveness of their application and limits the possibilities for the formation of comprehensive professional competencies of students. In the course of the research, the need for a transition to an integrated digital educational environment combining the possibilities of information modeling, geoinformation analysis and immersive interaction with the projected objects was theoretically substantiated. The developed conceptual model for the integration of BIM, GIS and VR/AR technologies allows for the continuity of all stages of the educational process — from the analysis of the territory and the development of design solutions to their visualization, evaluation and presentation. The results obtained indicate that the introduction of an integrated digital approach contributes to the development of spatial and systemic thinking, improving the quality of project training, the formation of interdisciplinary interaction skills and students' readiness for professional activity in the digital economy. Of particular importance is the possibility of modeling real-world project situations and creating a practice-oriented

educational environment that is as close as possible to the modern requirements of professional activity. The scientific significance of the research lies in the development of theoretical ideas about the digital transformation of landscape education and the substantiation of a model of a digital educational ecosystem based on the integration of BIM, GIS and VR/AR technologies. The practical significance lies in the possibility of using the proposed approaches in the modernization of educational programs, the development of digital platforms, the creation of virtual educational laboratories

and the improvement of methodological support for the training of landscape specialists. The prospects for further research are related to conducting a pedagogical experiment to evaluate the effectiveness of the developed model, studying the impact of integrated digital technologies on the formation of students' professional competencies, as well as developing intelligent educational platforms using artificial intelligence, digital twins and augmented reality technologies to train new generation specialists.

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